

Human Resource Sustainability and its Impact on the Competitive Performance of Banks: Evidence from Iraqi Private Banks

Shaymaa Tareq Majon¹, Dhamyaa Ghazi Hameed²

^{1,2}Ministry of Communication, Post & Saving public Company, Baghdad, Iraq

ARTICLE INFO

Online Publication:
11 July 2025

Corresponding Author:
Shaymaa Tareq Majon

KEYWORDS: Human Resources Sustainability, Competitive Performance of Banks, Iraqi Private Banks

ABSTRACT

Importance of this research stems from the pivotal role that sustainable human resources play in achieving institutional excellence and enhancing competitive capabilities. and Problem lies in weak implementation of human resources sustainability practices within private banks, which may negatively impact their competitive performance in a market undergoing constant change. In addition to Aims clarify the concept of human resources sustainability, analyse its reality in the Iraqi banking environment, and measure its impact on competitiveness, while providing recommendations that contribute to developing effective and sustainable strategies for managing the human resource. Through this, the research seeks to support decision-makers in private banks towards adopting sustainable policies that contribute to strengthening their position within the local and regional banking market. And main Hypothesis that implementation of human resources sustainability practices (such as continuous training, retaining talent, and achieving job satisfaction) contributes to effective competitive performance in Iraqi private banks. Results Human resource sustainability has a significant impact on the rise in competitive performance indicators, as we witnessed for BNOI bank with job satisfaction rates rising and employee turnover rates increasing in 2023.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources and individual competencies are considered human and intellectual capital and a strategic reserve represented by the capabilities and skills of workers and employees in private and public banks, which makes bank management work to organize and develop these resources to achieve human sustainability for current and future generations and make them an advantage for competitive performance among private banks. (Samlali, 2005). The key to competitiveness is for organizations to have advantages that give them superiority over their competitors, including providing services that are not implemented by competing banks, and distinguished and superior performance, such as adopting a specific strategy for competition, which is expressed through calculating indicators (financial, market, beneficiaries, human resources performance) In addition to environmental indicators The competitive performance of banks is affected by many factors, including internal factors such as human resources, their management and sustainability, management style and the bank's location, and external factors such as market conditions, competitors and government policies. (Atris, 2020).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Human Resources Sustainability (HRS):- Many organizations are trying to gain a larger market share and high profitability by making their revenues greater than their operating expenses and by having a distinguished performance to compete with other companies or banks. Competitive performance is defined as the ability of organizations to apply production processes that are not applied by competing organizations and the inability of these organizations to obtain the necessary resources to imitate those processes. The function of satisfying the needs and satisfaction of employees as internal customers and achieving internal satisfaction and achieving customer satisfaction in the market (Abu Qahf, 2018) Or it is known as the ability to measure financial, human and environmental indicators, as well as the ability to measure market indicators and determine the company's competitive position. (Abu Hasna K. , 2018). And with the ongoing threat to environmental resources, as well as consumption patterns that, in turn, threaten the integrity of

ecosystems and the well-being of future generations, the concept of sustainability has emerged within many modern environmental trends for several reasons, the most important of which is to compensate for the shortcomings resulting from the short-term viability of resources and activities. Companies and institutions based on this concept are pursuing it, and even treating it as a goal to be pursued. In its broadest sense, sustainability refers to the viability or sustainability of a process over time, enabling it to remain available over the long term. Its goal is to prevent the continued depletion of natural or material resources (Abdel Rahman & al-Bashar, 2025). As well as It refers to the management of human resources in a way that ensures that the current needs of the organization are met without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. It is a concept derived from the idea of general sustainability (environmental, economic and social), but it is applied to the human element within organizations (Shubar & Jassim, 2024). Human resource sustainability includes the following: (Mohamed, 2024).

- Retaining and developing talent through continuous training and professional development.
- Creating a healthy and safe work environment that motivates employees and maintains their mental and physical health.
- Fairness, diversity, and equality in hiring, promotions, and salaries.
- Long-term human resource planning to ensure a balance between present and future needs.
- Reducing employee turnover by enhancing job satisfaction and organizational loyalty.
- Focusing on ethical values and social responsibility in dealing with employees

2.2. Importance of Human Resources Sustainability:

- (Abu Hasna K. M., 2018).

- ✓ Achieving institutional stability by reducing employee turnover (resignations or terminations). It also helps maintain expertise and knowledge within the organization.
- ✓ Increased employee productivity and performance. Trained and motivated employees deliver higher performance. A sustainable work environment motivates employees to perform at a higher level.
- ✓ Enhancing employee loyalty and belonging. When employees feel valued and respected, they are more committed to their work. Sustainability creates strong bonds between employees and the organization.

- ✓ Improving the organization's image. Companies that prioritize their human resources attract the best talent. They also build a positive reputation locally and globally (Al-Diyasti, Arafa, & Zaazou, 2021).
- ✓ Supporting innovation and development. Investing in education and training opens the door to new ideas It also creates happy, confident employees who participate in initiatives and innovate solutions.
- ✓ Promoting social justice and ethical responsibility by embracing the principles of "decent work" and "equality." It reduces discrimination and supports diversity and empowerment within the workplace.
- ✓ Preparing for the future: The organization prepares to face technological and economic changes and helps plan the workforce according to future market needs.

2.3. Dimensions of Human Resource Sustainability are as follows: (Shubar & Jassim, 2024)

- Job retention: This refers to reducing the attrition of talent from the organization by providing a stable and stimulating work environment.
- Training and development: This relates to enhancing the professional skills and capabilities of employees to ensure their continued efficiency and adaptability to changes.
- Equality and ethical development: This includes achieving equality and transparency in treatment, and providing an ethical environment that respects human values.
- Work-life balance: This focuses on improving the quality of employees' work lives through policies that support a balance between personal and professional commitments.

2.4. Concept of Competitive Performance: -

Competitive performance is a measure of an institution's or companies (such as a bank's) ability to achieve market superiority and distinction compared to its competitors. This is achieved through a set of indicators and criteria that reflect its success and sustainability (Ramadan, 2020) Some people think Competitive performance in the banking sector is defined as a bank's ability to attract the largest number of customers, provide advanced financial services, and achieve strong financial results compared to other banks in the same market. Or it is the bank's ability to survive, grow, and outperform its competitors by utilizing its resources effectively and providing added value to customers and shareholders (Fairuz, 2024). From the concept of competitive performance of banks, we conclude that there are terms related to performance, which are as follows:

“Human Resource Sustainability and its Impact on the Competitive Performance of Banks: Evidence from Iraqi Private Banks”

Effectiveness is a tool for measuring an organization's ability to achieve its planned goals. Based on this, an organization's effectiveness is measured by the ratio of its actual results to what it intended to achieve according to the plan.

- ❖ **Efficiency:-** "means the ability to reduce or minimize waste in the organization's available resources, by using resources appropriately according to specific scheduling criteria (i.e., the amount of output or outcomes within a specific time), quality, and cost. Therefore, it is a concept of rational use of human, material, financial, and available information resources. It is also defined as "the ability to perform the required work with minimal resources, and efficient activity is the least costly activity." Efficiency is calculated using the following relationship: **output value divided by input value.** (Samlali, 2005)
- ❖ **Effectiveness:-** not only means achieving set goals, but also reflects the proper selection of these goals. It is also "the organization's ability to achieve its

strategic objectives of growing sales and maximizing its market share compared to competitors." Effectiveness is calculated according to the following relationship: Achievement achieved divided by Specified achievement

- ❖ **Productivity:-** is optimal use of production elements, in order to achieve greatest possible amount of production at a specific quality level and variety, at a specific time, and at lowest possible cost, which gives highest possible surplus of profitability. Productivity is based on a relationship between outputs and production factors, and occurs when an increase in output is coupled with a less proportionate increase in production factors, or when the same output is produced with fewer production factors. productivity of the institution is linked to efficiency and effectiveness, Productivity is calculated by combining efficiency with effectiveness (Mahboub, 2016). and this is what the following figure shows.

Figure1. Shows the Relationship between Productivity, Efficiency and Effectiveness
 Source: (Ahmed, 2000)

2.5. Characteristics of Competitive Performance in Banking Sector: (Abdel Wahab , 2024)

- Quality of Banking Services: Competitive performance is characterized by providing distinguished and rapid financial services that meet the diverse needs of customers (financing, transfers, deposits, etc.) with high quality.
- Technological Innovation: Relying on modern technology in providing banking services (such as digital services, electronic payments, and banking applications) to increase efficiency and attract customers.
- Regulatory and Legal Compliance: Achieving compliance with banking

regulations and laws, which enhances the bank's confidence and competitive reputation in the market.

- Risk Management Capability: Effectively managing financial and credit risks avoiding losses and ensuring the bank's stability and continuity.
- Achieving Customer Satisfaction: Focusing on building strong relationships with customers through excellent customer service and continuous support, which increases customer loyalty. (Fatima, 2016)
- Operational Efficiency: Achieving efficient banking operations that reduce costs and increase productivity, which is reflected in

the bank's financial performance (Al-Rahman, 2024).

- Diversity of Products and Services: Offering a wide range of banking products to meet the requirements of various customer segments, which enhances the bank's competitiveness.
- Reputation and Credibility: Building a positive image in the market through transparent transactions and credible financial and administrative performance.
- Focus on sustainability: Adopting human and financial resource sustainability practices that help the bank maintain its competitive strength over the long term (Tawati, 2023).

2.6. Dimensions of Competitive Performance in Banking Sector:

- **Financial Dimension:** - includes profitability indicators (such as return on assets and return on capital), financial efficiency, liquidity, and the level of non-performing loans. It reflects the bank's ability to achieve sustainable financial returns and improve its financial position.
- **Service Quality Dimension:** - relates to the provision of distinguished financial services, rapid customer response, and transaction accuracy. It directly impacts customer satisfaction and loyalty.
- **Technological and Innovation Dimension:** - includes the use of modern technologies such as electronic banking services, smartphone applications, and digital payment systems. It enhances the ability to attract new customers and improve the user experience.
- **Operational Dimension:** - relates to the efficiency of the bank's internal processes, such as cost management, transaction processing speed, and error reduction. It helps improve the bank's overall performance and reduce expenses (Hassan, 2024).
- **Regulatory and Compliance Dimension:** - includes the bank's compliance with local and international banking laws and regulations. It enhances the bank's reputation and reduces legal and regulatory risks.
- **Human Resources Dimension:** - relates to the quality and efficiency of human resources, training and development programs, and employee satisfaction. It is reflected in the level of service provided and innovative solutions.
- **Marketing Dimension:** - and market share include the ability to attract new customers,

retain existing customers, and expand market share. It reflects the bank's influence in the market and its position among competitors.

- **Strategic Dimension:** - includes the bank's clarity of vision and strategic objectives and its ability to adapt to economic and technological changes. It ensures sustainable competitive advantage over the long term (Zawawi, 2021)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Dependent variable:** Human Resource Sustainability
- **Independent variables:** the Competitive Performance of Banks
- **Descriptive analysis:** researchers will review research sample, which consists of two banks, and will measure research sample indicators for years (2020- 2024) , as shown below:

❖ **National Bank of Iraq (BNOI) Company Scope:** The National Bank of Iraq (known as: National Bank) is a public company listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange since July 2004. The National Bank operates in the banking sector. The National Bank is headquartered in Baghdad, Iraq, and was established in January 1995. The bank's capital amounts to 250 billion dinars. The bank is affiliated with the Jordanian Capital Bank and has 12 branches in Iraq (BNOI,2024)

❖ **Gulf Commercial Bank (BGUC):** is an Iraqi bank. It was established as a private joint stock company under Certificate of Incorporation No. 7002/dated 10/20/1999 issued by the Companies Registration Department in accordance with Companies Law No. (21) Of 1997 with a capital of (600,000,000) dinars paid in full. It started its actual activity on 4/1/2000 and main branch opened its doors to the public on that date after obtaining a banking license from Central Bank of Iraq No. S.A./9/3/115 dated 2/7/2000 in accordance with provisions of Central Bank of Iraq Law No. (64) Of 1976, which was repealed, for the bank to practice comprehensive banking activities Its Articles of Association were amended by increasing its capital several times until its capital became (250) billion dinars on 9/8/2013 (BGUC, 2024).

Now, researchers will calculate Human Resources Sustainability through following:

1. **Employee Retention Rate (ERR)= Number of Employees Remaining at End of Period / Number of Employees at Beginning of the Period x 100**

“Human Resource Sustainability and its Impact on the Competitive Performance of Banks: Evidence from Iraqi Private Banks”

2. **Employee Turnover Rate(ETR) = Average Number of Employees During Period / Number of Employees Who Left During Period x 100**
3. **Satisfaction Index (SI) = Total Employee Ratings / Maximum Possible Ratings x 100**

4. **Training Investment Ratio (TIR) = Training and Development Cost / Total Payroll Cost x 100**

Table below shows calculation Human Resources Sustainability for National Bank of Iraq and Gulf Commercial Bank for period from 2020 to 2024

Table1. Shows Calculating of Employee Retention Rate, Employee Turnover Rate, Satisfaction Index, Training Investment Ratio for National Bank of Iraq and Gulf Commercial Bank for Period 2020-2024

years	National Bank of Iraq (BNOI)				Gulf Commercial Bank (BGUC)			
	¹ ERR	² ETR	³ SI	⁴ TIR	ERR	ETR	SI	TIR
2020	100.58	8,625	97.98	0.23	93.13	0.510	91.60	2.212903
2021	88.46	0.433	99.13	0.27	85.71	0.810	100.00	2.623084
2022	96.06	1,269	97.44	0.20	110.67	1,929	98.94	0.143537
2023	104.10	1,219	99.01	0.24	73.33	1,625	99.80	0.272881
2024	95.82	1,188	98.97	0.20	99.14	2,020	99.42	0.343933

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on data from the two banks

From table above, we conclude that highest percentage was achieved by bank (BNOI) in 2023 and lowest percentage in 2021, and that these percentages are higher Compared to bank

(BGUC), and figure below illustrates sustainable human resources indicators for two banks for period 2020-2024.

Figure 2. Shows Human Resources Sustainable Indicators for banks (BNOI) and (BGUC) for period 2020-2024

Source: Prepared by researchers based on data for banks 2020-2024.

And now we calculation competitive performance indicators among the most important competitive performance indicators are:

1. **Market Share (MSH) = (Company Sales / Total Market Sales) x 100**

2. **Revenue Growth Rate (RGR) = (Current Period Sales - Previous Period Sales / Previous Period Sales) x 100**

3. **Net Profit Margin(NPM) = (Net Profit / Revenue) x 100**

1 It represents the employee retention rate

2 It represents the employee turnover rate

3 It represents the satisfaction index

4 It represents the percentage Training Investment Ratio

“Human Resource Sustainability and its Impact on the Competitive Performance of Banks: Evidence from Iraqi Private Banks”

Table below illustrates calculation for National Bank of Iraq and Gulf Commercial Bank for period from 2020 to 2024.

Table 2. Shows ⁵Calculating Market Share, Revenue Growth Rate, and Profitability for National Bank of Iraq and Gulf Commercial Bank for Period 2020-2024

years	National Bank of Iraq (BNOI)			Gulf Commercial Bank (BGUC)		
	⁶ MSH	⁷ RGR	⁸ NPM	MSH	RGR	NPM
2020	0.0246226	1,250,062,031,900	0.044960329	0.0098754	0,578,830,209,876	0.009960365
2021	0.0225804	1,357,643,031,900	0.047363849	0.0642876	0,467,689,346,787	0.007368876
2022	0.0249393	1,250,062,031,900	0.004962314	0.0854732	0,574,332,778,980	0.009562314
2023	0.0294120	1,487,906,203,100	0.667225217	0.0467382	1,067,906,203,198	0.067225654
2024	0.0201836	1,286,762,031,900	0.059220896	0.0674303	1,386,762,037,641	0.087220896

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on data from the two banks

From table above, we conclude that highest percentage was achieved by bank (BNOI) in 2023 and lowest percentage in 2021, and that these percentages are higher Compared to bank

(BGUC), and now we calculation competitive performance indicators. And figure below illustrates competitive performance indicators for two banks for period 2020-2024

Figure3. Shows Competitive Performance Indicators for banks (BNOI) and (BGUC) for period 2020-2024

Source: Prepared by researchers based on data for banks 2020-2024

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Now that we have calculated sustainable human resources indicators and competitive performance indicators for banks, we will highlight the impact of sustainability on performance through the performance indicators and then the table shown below.

- ❖ Effectiveness = Achieved Goals / Planned Goals
- ❖ Efficiency = Outputs / Inputs
- ❖ Productivity = Effectiveness + Efficiency

⁵ Amounts are calculated in Iraqi dinars.

⁶ It is an abbreviation for market share.

⁷ It is an abbreviation for revenue growth rate.

⁸ It is an abbreviation for the bank's profitability.

Table 3. Shows Calculating of Effectiveness, Efficiency and Productivity for National Bank of Iraq and Gulf Commercial Bank for period 2020-2024

years	National Bank of Iraq (BNOI)			Gulf Commercial Bank (BGUC)		
	Effectiveness	Efficiency	Productivity	Effectiveness	Efficiency	Productivity
2020	0.85611455	2.763169753	3.61928430	0.4567457	1.8731698	2.3299154
2021	0.76766150	3.254757456	4.02241895	0.4476725	0.2987575	0.7464299
2022	0.99595595	2.583535760	3.57949171	0.6574839	1.0583535	1.7158375
2023	0.83661234	3.197439460	4.03405180	0.4326790	1.0197440	1.4524229
2024	0.85766725	2.565516701	3.42318395	0.7654390	1.2200167	1.9854557

From previous table, we note that **BNOI** Bank achieves higher productivity compared to competitive performance of **BGUC** Bank. **BNOI** Bank achieved highest productivity rate in 2023, due to higher employee satisfaction and employee retention rates compared to previous years. It recorded lowest

productivity rate in 2024, due to exclusion of some long-serving employees, which negatively impacted bank's competitive performance. And figure below illustrates Productivity for National Bank of Iraq and Gulf Commercial Bank for period 2020-2024

Figure 4. Shows Productivity for banks (BNOI) and (BGUC) for period 2020-2024

Source: Prepared by researchers based on data for banks 2020-2024

CONCLUSION

- Human resource sustainability has a significant impact on the rise in competitive performance indicators, as we witnessed for **BNOI** bank with job satisfaction rates rising and employee turnover rates increasing in 2023.
- Bank **BNOI** achieved highest percentage of human resource sustainability indicators compared to **BGUC** Bank.
- Bank **BNOI** achieved the highest percentage of competitive performance indicators compared to **BGUC** Bank.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We thank two banks National Bank of Iraq (BNOI) and Gulf Commercial Bank (BGUC) for providing all their data, information, and accounts. We also thank their staff and employees, especially general managers of the banks, for their support.

REFERENCES

1. Abdel Halim, M. (2012). Improving the performance of the enterprise under. Research submitted to complete the requirements for obtaining, 1-192. Retrieved from http://193.194.83.98/jspui/bitstream/1635/12029/1/MEZGHICHE_ABDELHALIUM.PDF.pdf

2. Abdel Rahman, A. A., & al-Bashar, M. M.-S. (2025). The relationship between environmental sustainability standards, improving environmental performance, and their interactive impact on the predictive power of accounting information in Saudi business establishments. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 4-5. doi:10.21608/abj.2025.411351
3. Abu Hasna, K. M. (2018). The role of technology leadership in improving competitive performance: a field study applied to Palestinian information and communications technology companies. *Scientific Journal of Business and Environmental Studies*, 822.
4. Abu Qahf, A. (2018). How to control the markets (Learn from the Japanese experience). Alexandria University, 822.
5. Aissa, K., Soumia, F., & Abdelraouf, A. (2021). Evaluate the financial performance of commercial banks using financial ratios- A study of a group of Algerian commercial banks during the period 2015-2019. *Economic Science Management and Business Science*, 14(1), 31-46. Retrieved from <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/154219>
6. Al-Ayeb, A., & Buqa, S. (2012). A reading of the state's supportive role to improve the sustainable environmental performance of economic institutions. Setif University, 82-94.
7. Al-Diyasti, D. H., Arafa, M. M., & Zaazou, Z. A. (2021). The impact of applying the sustainable balanced scorecard on improving the competitive performance of Egyptian ports: an applied study on West Port Said Port. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Researches*, 552.
8. Fairuz, B. (2024). Human resources management for local communities. Faculty of Economics, Business and Management Sciences.
9. Ibrahim, T., & Al Masoud, R. (2021, jun). Evaluating the financial performance of Islamic banks using the return on assets and return on equity indicators, applying to Qatar Islamic Bank and Jordan Islamic Bank during the period 2008-2018. *Journal of Financial, Accounting and Administrative Studies*, 8(2), 595-617. Retrieved from <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/58/8/2/162418>
10. Mahboub, F. (2016). The impact of strategic alliances on the competitive performance of industrial enterprises: a case study of the Soidal Group. Faculty of Economics, Business and Management Sciences, 90.
11. Ramadan, I. A.-S. (2020). The impact of participatory leadership on improving the competitive performance of Egyptian hotels. *International Journal of Heritage, Tourism and Hospitality*, 114.
12. Samlali, Y. (2005). Knowledge management and improving the competitive performance of the economic institution. *International Scientific Conference on Outstanding Performance of Organizations and Governments* (p. 423). Algeria: University of Ouargla - Faculty of Law and Economics.
13. Shubar, R. K., & Jassim, M. A. (2024). The Role of Evidence-Based Human Resource Management Practices in Human Resources Sustainability - An Empirical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Workers at the Kufa Cement Plant. *Al-Ghary Journal of Economic and Administrative Science*, 1292.
14. Abdel Wahab, S. I. (2024). The impact of marketing prowess on the competitive performance of companies: an applied study on mobile telecommunications services companies in Egypt. *Raya International Journal of Business Sciences*, 633.
15. Abdulkarim, M. (2017). Cleaner production technology and its role in protecting the environment and upgrading the industrial establishment. *Université Hassiba Benbouali de Chlef*, 246-265.
16. Ahmed, M. (2000). *Organizational Behavior: A Skills-Building Approach*. University House, Alexandria, 31.
17. Al-Mamari, A. G., & AL-Mawla, H. J. (2010). Evaluation of the efficiency of the economic performance of the General Company for the Pharmaceutical Industry in Nineveh for the period (2002-2007) a comparative analytical study. *Rafidain Development*, 99(32), 1-33. Retrieved from https://tanmiyat.mosuljournals.com/pdf_161878_d77b90b9a44ed9832b6a9cc8b8acf6e9.html
18. Al-Rahman, I. S. (2024). The Impact of Entrepreneurship on Sustainable Competitive Performance / Field Research in a Sample of Private Colleges. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Studies (JAFS)*, 52.
19. Al-Shabbasi, M. S., Youssef, H. Z., & Ashmawi, F. A. (2016). *Scientific Journal of Research and Business Studies - Faculty of Commerce - Helwan University*, 4(2), 1-32. Retrieved from <https://sjrbs.journals.ekb.eg>
20. ASADI, S. k., & ALmshhdani, s. M. (2021). The Use of LEED Criteria's for the Sustainability of Laboratory Quality Their Role in Rationalizing the Costs of Environmental Remediation. *Academy of*

- Accounting and Financial Studies Journal, 25(s4 -), 1-13. Retrieved from <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/the-rationalizing-costs-of-environmental-remediation-through-implementing-lead-criterias-for-the-sustainability-of-laboratory-qual-12366.html>
21. Atiyah, I. R. (2018). Integration of value stream method with cleaner production technique and its role in enhancing key success factors. In I. R. Atiyah, Integration of value stream method with cleaner production technique and its role in enhancing key success factors (p. 1). Baghdad: Higher Institute of Accounting and Financial Studies.
 22. Atris, M. (2020). Strategic leadership as an approach to improving the competitive performance of Egyptian universities in light of the sustainable development strategy: Egypt's Vision 2020 "Saqaiziq University as a model". Educational journal , 795. doi:10.12816/EDUSOHAG. 2020
 23. Cresswell, J. (2021, 8 15). Oxford Dictionary of Word Origins. (3, Ed.) OUP Oxford. Retrieved from <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com>.
 24. Fatima, M. (2016). The Impact of Strategic Alliances on the Competitive Performance of Industrial Firms: A Case Study of the Saidal Group. Faculty of Economics, Business and Management Sciences, 76.
 25. Hanoun, W. S. (2015, 10 29). The internal control system and its role in promoting cleaner production technology and its implications for sustainable development. The internal control system and its role in promoting cleaner production technology and its implications for sustainable development. baghdad, baghdad, iraq: Higher Institute of Accounting and Financial Studies.
 26. Hassan, M. M. (2024). A proposed vision to improve the environmental performance of the Egyptian Society in light of the Green World Standard for GMWUR. Journal of the College of Education, 32.
 27. Iain , K., & Buckley, C. A. (2010). A CLEANER PRODUCTION PROJECT IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN PAPER INDUSTRY – LESSONS LEARNT. Conference: WasteCon 2010At: Johannesburg, South Africa (pp. 1-9). WasteCon: ResearchGate. doi:10.13140/2.1.3508.5448
 28. Khalif , A. M. (2014). The role of green accounting in supporting cleaner production technology / an applied study in Ur State Company for Engineering Industries. Master's thesis, College of Administration and Economics, Al-Mustansiriya University., 46.
 29. Laalmi, F. B. (2019). Cleaner production as a basic orientation for environmental management systems and sustainable development: a case study of Germany. Cleaner production, environmental management system, economic institutions, sustainable development (pp. 1-13). turkish: Espace numerique Universite Abd El Hamid Ibn Badis Mostaganem. Retrieved from <http://e-biblio.univ-mosta.dz/handle/123456789/7664>
 30. Mohamed, R. K. (2024). Green human resource management practices and their relationship to enhancing organizational sustainability at Sohag University. College of Education Educational Journal, 188.
 31. Mulholland, K. L. (2006). Identification of cleaner production improvement opportunities. John Wiley & Sons.
 32. Paul Folan, J. B. (2007). Performance: its meaning and content for today's business research. Computer in industry, 58(7), 605-620. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2007.05.002>
 33. Tawati, M. (2023). Competitive performance of Algerian industry. Faculty of Economics, Business and Management Sciences, 104.
 34. U.S. Department of Labor, O. S. (2022). Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA). USA. <https://web.archive.org/web/20220509225256/https://www.osha.gov/chemicaldata/>
 35. www.google.come. (n.d.). www.google.come. Retrieved from https://www.google.com/search?q=الدورة+مصفي&client=opera&hs=aHh&sxsrf=ALiCzsaV5Q1WvDesb sJXOXEYz-6CzmPZ_Q:1660661630689&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwj-d-NrUzsv5AhUoQPEDHekUCqMQ_AUoAnoECAIQBA&cshid=1660661754173522&biw=1093&bih=494&dpr=1.69
 36. Zawawi, F. (2021). Strategic analysis as a tool for improving the competitive performance of institutions. Journal of Development and Foresight for Research and Studies, 76.
 37. (BNOI), The National Bank of Iraq, (2024) , Annual reports with bank data.
 38. (BGUC),Gulf Commercial Bank, (2024) , Annual reports with bank data.
 39. Bank of Baghdad, (2024) , Annual reports with bank data.